

Sharing Agreements and Quality attributes in Data Manufacturing

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Keywords: data sharing agreements (DSAs); data quality; data manufacturing; argumentation reasoning

Topic(s): Operations Innovation, Technology Management in Operations, Information Systems in Operations

Abstract

Purpose: Contemporary advancements in technology coupled with the “Big Data” evolution of the last decade provides access to data resources in an unprecedented way, as well as opportunities to innovate through the use of data generated, collected and transformed to actionable knowledge (Delen and Demirkan, 2013). The Knowledge Economy and more specifically the proliferation of data (George et al., 2014) has altered also the way firms compete and work for value creation, and has reshaped the manufacturing landscape toward value co-creation among firms (Lusch and Vargo, 2006). New data-intensive ways of creating value are introduced and require additionally to analytical tools and techniques, sense making skills (Weick, 1995) as the main challenge of organizations for data-based decision-making (Lycett, 2013). Literature reviews about the manufacturing context reveal that the data evolution has influenced radically also the production and service industries (Mishra et al., 2016; Wamba et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016). The last decade there is a hype of service industries around data (for storing, analyzing, processing etc.), where data are shared as well

as stored, used and transformed, not only by users but also by organizations, public sector and third parties. Data processing challenges are not new, however previous eras of data management were focusing solely on the quality of data of a single database (Hazen et al., 2014), what is new is the expansive way the data processing works; across the immediate boundaries of the firm, the industrial sector or even the country.

Data processing was initially introduced by Brodie (1980) through the analogy between product manufacturing and data manufacturing when data quality was a primary concern in transforming data to valid information and knowledge (Arnold, 1992). Some of the most indicative studies around these areas developed the concept of data manufacturing analogy in order to find out the path for better data quality (Arnold, 1992; Huh et al., 1990; March and Hevner, 2007) while framing and tracking the data manufacturing process (Pipino et al., 2002; Strong et al., 1997; Wang, 1998; Wang et al., 1995). In our study we focus on expanding the data manufacturing analogy with a focus on data sharing agreements (DSAs), and the quality attributes of the data. Exchanging data implies that all parties agree on the associated rules to be enforced; which is often referred as a data sharing agreement (Swarup et al., 2006). The data sharing agreement (DSA) can be seen as a contract, between two or more parties, and the different rules are the terms of the contract.

Methodology: The proposed approach extends the data manufacturing analogy and focuses on data processing by various entities and the associated data sharing agreements (DSAs). The study proposes an expressive policy analysis language for representing the DSAs through argumentation reasoning, enriched with data quality attributes to capture aspects of the data. The introduced analysis permits the construction of correct and efficient DSAs that apply in different contexts during the processing of data.

Contributions and expected findings: The purpose of this research is to extend the ‘data manufacturing’ concept of previous decades, to a data-intensive environment across organisational, individual and country boundaries, where data are accessible by different entities. By using the data processing approach, we unfold the potential areas of interest of data manufacturing for multiple entities. Within this context, we argue that data can be processed and can create value through tailoring techniques across organisational boundaries with the help of DSAs and usage control rules while developing data products/services as well as disrupting the manufacturing landscape to facilitate such a change.

Acknowledgments

Erisa Karafili was supported by the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 746667.

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